

Navigating the Evolving Landscape of Research Data Governance in Libraries: Insights from PRISMA Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

The swift expansion of research data governance and its impact on data integrity, security, and standards has increased global recognition of the importance of research data. Libraries play crucial roles in managing the flow of research data by providing access to it and enhancing its security and integrity, thereby improving research data service delivery. Despite this, there is a noticeable gap in the literature explicitly identifying libraries as a trending topic in data governance.

Methodology: This study aims to identify the trending topics in data governance through a systematic literature review, following the PRISMA 2009 method as outlined in the flow diagram by Moher et al. (2009). The review focuses on published contributions from 2018 to 2022.

Hypothesis: The hypothesis is that research data governance (RDG) is primarily discussed in fields related to Information Technology and Computer Science, rather than in libraries.

Findings/Results: The review uncovered 36 articles reflecting the current state of topics in research data governance. The findings revealed that no articles directly addressed research data governance in libraries; instead, RDG was primarily discussed in related fields such as Information Technology and Computer Science. Other disciplines researched in RDG included public/smart cities, business/economic institutions, public health institutions, public security institutions, and the agricultural sector.

Conclusion: The study concludes that there is a significant gap in the literature regarding research data governance in libraries. This gap highlights the need for more focused research in this area.

Recommendations: The study recommends that librarians engage more deeply in exploring research data governance and collaborate with computer science and IT specialists. The

creation of an effective, functional research and IT team for data governance tasks, along with a framework for regulatory compliance procedures, should be prioritized in institutional library management to support RDG implementations.

Keywords: *Research Data Governance, Systematic Literature Review, Data Governance in Libraries, PRISMA Methodology*

Introduction

Information and data management are the central nervous systems of any library, providing the smooth flow of day-to-day operations and crucial decision-making processes. Data complexity and explosion drive new demands requiring different ways to combine, manipulate, store, and present information. Libraries are adopting web-based technologies and the internet in their daily tasks to promote cost reduction and better resource utilization. Recognizing the notion of data governance solutions, libraries started to take a different direction.

They were driven by IT and were affected by rigid processes and fragmented activities carried out on a system-by-system basis. Data Governance has been mostly informal, in silos around specific enterprise repositories, lacking structure and the wider support of the organization (Al-Ruithe & Benkhelifa, 2020). Despite data governance's high importance (Nwabugu & Godwin, 2020; Alsousi, & Shah, 2022; Liu, Li & Jomaas, 2022), it is still an under-researched area and not a common practice around librarianship, especially in underdeveloped countries.

Research data management has been called a “ground-breaking” area for research libraries and it is among the top future trends for academic libraries (Ashiq, Usmani & Naeem, 2020) with insignificant evidence of research data governance (RDG). The notion of data governance as a way of determining the allocation of information decision-making rights within a firm (Yin & Li, 2022; Matheus, Janssen, & Maheshwari, 2020) is the art of managing information tools and creation, capture, and evaluation of digital information value within an organization.

To achieve successful data governance in libraries, a comprehensive literature review to explore a strategic framework that can be easily implemented under the needs and resources of information becomes imperative. Research on data governance is limited and lacks key perspective and it can only be continuously valuable if supported by a holistic systematic analysis focused on sustainability (Bento, Neto & Côte-Real, 2022) A systematic literature review on studies related to data governance can create a clear mission and framework to achieve clarity and increase confidence to maintain scope and focus and define measurable successes.

It is necessary to theoretically integrate and synthesize the vast body of knowledge in data governance to identify strategies and success factors and provide valid research directions for libraries. This study goes beyond prior research (including Al-Ruithe & Benkhelifa, 2020; 1,

2022; Alsousi, & Shah, 2022; Liu, Li & Jomaas, 2022) by demonstrating and considering the widely implicitly and tacitly assumed conceptual autonomy of data governance for drawing differentiated and valid conclusions for libraries. Building on and extending the general conceptual development of RDG by consolidating previous research perspectives from the literature is essential to outline the role of academic advancement in the research data governance ecosystem.

To establish a best practice for data governance among librarians, a systematic literature review as a methodology was carried out to identify, evaluate and interpret all available research relevant to data governance. Therefore, the literature review as a research method is more relevant than ever as presented by Snyder (2019), that the traditional literature reviews often lack thoroughness and rigor and are conducted ad hoc, rather than following a specific methodology. This will produce varied and reliable results with little bias that can occur in other approaches and will serve as the basis for further empirical studies. Therefore, this literature review provides a comprehensive overview of Research Data Governance (RDG) and the relevant facets embedded in this research stream using the process described by the PRISMA 2009 flow diagram of Moher *et al.* (2009). The systematic review adopted the stages of Identification, Screening, Eligibility, and Inclusion as a means of identifying, evaluating, and interpreting all available research relevant to answering the research question.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to explore and understand the position of academic libraries and analyze systematically, the most relevant published research that has been carried out on Research Data Governance (RDG) between 2018 and 2022 using the PRISMA diagram This paper focuses on the following three research questions (RQ):

RQ1: How is the concept of research data governance (RDG) conceptually defined in literature as a building block of data governance?

RQ2: What is the classification of research discipline as the area of concern by authors of research data governance?

RQ3: What are the authorship dimensions of research data governance studies?

Research Methods

The methodology of the study is largely exploratory research conducted because the phenomenon of research data governance in academic libraries is not clearly defined. Though, the study does not aim to provide the final and conclusive answers to the research questions but merely, to explore the research topic with varying levels of depth to serve as the foundation for future empirical investigation around RDG implementation in libraries. This research

employed the systematic literature review, as described by the PRISMA 2009 flow diagram of Moher *et al.* (2009). The systematic review method was conducted by using the stages of Identification, Screening, Eligibility, and Inclusion means of identifying, evaluating and interpreting all available research relevant to answering the research question. Furthermore, the PRISMA flow diagram analysis revealed the relationship of the topics to each other of records related to research data governance published between 2018 and 2022.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Eligibility criteria are based on the study design, and date of publication. Exclusion criteria mostly are unrelated, duplicated, unavailable abstracts stated in advance to refrain the researcher from bias. The inclusion criteria are articles with the targeted data governance and information management containing information answering the current study research question including both positive and negative, to answer the question.

Table 1: Search Strategy

Inclusion - Exclusion Criteria		Search Database	
Language:	English only	ScienceDirect	2,632
Search String:	Research Data Governance (RDG) / Research Data Management (RDM)	Emerald	45
Time Range:	From 2018 to 2022	Springer	474
Database	Title, abstract, Keywords	Google Scholar	3,590
Search Fields			
Document Type	Journal Article, Conference Paper	Semantic Scholar	1,100
		Other Sources	212
		Total:	8,053
Screening and Filtering		Related titles on RDG / RDM Articles	120
		Titles and Abstract treating only RDG excluding RDM	36

The inclusion criteria of the study for the eligibility factor were:

- Studies published between the years 2018 to 2022.
- Studies published in English language only.
- Document type included only research articles and conference papers.
- Studies that cover aspects of Research Data Governance.

The exclusion criteria were based on:

- Studies published before 2018 and not beyond 2022.
- Studies published in other languages.
- Book and book chapters, newspaper, and Magazine.
- Studies on data mining and technology.
- Studies covering only aspects of Research Data Management.

Data Analysis

A broad search strategy was made to extract the maximum relevant data from the five databases purposively selected by the study. In this section, we discuss the state of knowledge regarding RDG as documented in the reviewed articles. Each dimension of the conceptual framework was broken down to provide an overview of the findings and insights.

Fig. 2: Flow Diagram of Selection Procedure of the Study

(Source: The original diagram was adapted from PRISMA Group; Moher, *et al.*, 2009)

The study systematically searched for articles in different databases, including ScienceDirect (2,632 records), Emerald (45 records), Springer (474 records), Google Scholar (3,590 records), Semantic Scholar (1,100 records), and other sources (212 records). The process found 8,053 records published between 2018 and 2022 related articles to data governance, data

management, data application, and regulations, most of which did not meet the required criteria of the study. This number was screened to 850 by filtering out misleading titles, records without contents, bibliometric articles, review articles, and presentations, this process produced 120 records. The records were further filtered based on relevant titles, abstracts and availability of contents which produced 36 records dealing directly with data governance useful for the study. The 36 records were filtered based on the set criteria of uniqueness, completeness, time-framed study, and accessibility.

Overview of selected studies

The extracted information from the selected studies is provided in Table 2. The first column provides the serial number of the records, the second column provides title information of the articles, the third shows author information and year of publication, the fourth column specifies the journal name where the articles were published, and the last column identifies the publisher of the journal or conference proceeding.

Table 2: Characteristics of the Selected Studies

S/No	Title of Article	Author / Year	Journal Name	Publisher
1.	A new fuzzy approach for managing data governance implementation relevant activities	Ahmadi, Tavana, Shokouhyar & Dortaj (2022)	The TQM Journal, 34(5) 979-1012	Emerald Publications
2.	Indonesian Scientists' Behavior of Research Data Governance in Preventing WMD-Applicable Technology Transfer	Manik, Akbar, Yaman & Indrawati (2022)	Publications 10(50), 1-29	MDPI
3.	Governance and stewardship for research data and information sharing: Issues and prospective solutions in the transdisciplinary plant phenotyping and imaging research center network.	Awada, Phillips & Bogdan (2022)	Plants People & Planet; 4(1): 84-95	Wiley
4.	Data Governance for SME: Systematic Literature Review	Al-Sousi & Shah (2022)	Journal of Information Systems and Digital Technologies, 4(2), 49-57	

5.	Research on Police Data Governance Process	Shi, Li, Wang & Zhang (2022)	Journal of Academic Simulation, 10(2), 85-94	Academic Publishing House
6.	Revamping Nigeria's economy through sustainable data governance	Aguboshim, Obiokafor & Ezeife (2022)	World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 14(01), 616-623	
7.	How data governance frameworks can leverage data-driven decision making: A sustainable approach for data governance in organizations	Bento, Neto & Côte-Real (2022)	2022 17th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI), Spain 1-5.	IEEE
8.	Information Technology Strategy: A Case for Data Governance	Patel (2022)	Procedia Computer Science Journal (No. 8120) 1-6	EasyChair
9.	Performative innovation: Data governance in China's fintech industries	Wang (2022)	Big Data & Society, 9(2) 1-11	Sage
10.	An Investigation into the Role of Data Governance in Improving Data Quality: A Case Study of the Omani Banking Sector	Al Wahshi, Foster & Abbott (2022)	Proceedings; 30th European Conference on Information Systems – ECIS, 18-24 Jun 2022, Romania, 1-16	White Rose University Consortium
11.	Designing data governance in Brazil: an institutional analysis	Filgueiras & Lui (2022)	Policy Design and Practice, 1-16	Informa UK Limited
12.	A Literature Review of Data Governance and Its Applicability to Smart Cities	Bozkurt, Rossmann & Pervez (2022)	Proceedings of the 55th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences 2022	
13.	Improving Data Quality and Data Governance Using Master Data Management: A Review	Hikmawati, Santosa & Hidayah (2021)	International Journal of Information Technology and Electrical Engineering	Universitas Gadjah Mada

			(IJITEE), 5(3), 90-95	
14.	Data Governance and its Scientific Outlook in Indonesia: A Literature Review.	Ramadhan, Jaafar & Tajudeen, (2021)	Journal of Management Information and Decision Sciences, 24(3), 1-10.	
15.	An ontological-based model to data governance for big data.	Castro, Villagra, Garca, Rivera & Toledo (2021)	IEEE Access, 9, 1-17	IEEE
16.	Data Governance: A Conceptual Framework for SME	Shah & AISousi (2021)	The Middle East International Journal for Social Sciences (MEIJSS) 3(3):158-163	
17.	Research on the construction of data governance organization for digital traffic	Chang & Kang (2021)	Proc. of International Conference on Signal Processing and Communication Technology (SPCT 2021), China; SPIE Vol. 12178, 121782C	
18.	An Exploratory Study of Research Data Governance in the U.S.	Kouper, Raymond & Giroux (2020)	Open Information Science; 4: 122–142	De Gruyter
19.	Emerging models of data governance in the age of datafication	Micheli, Ponti, Craglia & Suman (2020)	Big Data & Society, 7(2)	Sage Publication
20.	Data governance: Organizing data for trustworthy Artificial Intelligence	Janssen, Brous, Estevez, Barbosa & Janowski (2020)	Government Information Quarterly, 37(3), 1-8	Elsevier ScienceDirect
21.	Trusted decision-making: Data governance for	Brous & Janssen (2020)	Administrative Sciences, 10(4), 1-19	MDPI

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- creating trust in data science decision outcomes
22. Towards an integrated model of data governance and integration for the implementation of digital transformation processes in Saudi universities Omar & Almagthawi (2020) International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, 11(8), 588-593 The Science and Information Organization (SAI)
23. Data Governance as a Collective Action Problem. Benfeldt, Persson & Madsen (2020) Information Systems Frontiers, 22, 299-313
24. Applying Data Governance Based on COBIT2019 Framework to Achieve Sustainable Development Goals. Thabit, Ishhadat & Abdulrahman (2020) Journal of Middle Technical University, 2(3), 9-18
25. Emerging health data platforms: From individual control to collective data governance Kariotis, Ball, Tzovaras, Dennis, Sahama, Johnston, Almond & Borda (2020) Data & Policy, 2(e-13), 1-12 Cambridge University Press
26. Towards a Data Governance Framework for Third-Generation Platforms Yebenes & Zorrilla (2019) Procedia Computer Science, 151, 614-621 Elsevier ScienceDirect
27. Systematic Literature Review of Data Governance and Cloud Data Governance. Al-Ruithe, Benkhelifa & Hameed (2019) Personal and Ubiquitous Computing; 23(5-6), 839-859 Elsevier ScienceDirect
28. Data Governance as the Enabler of the Data Economy Engels (2019) Intereconomics, 54(4), 216-222 Springer
29. Data governance: A conceptual framework, structured review, and research agenda. Abraham, Schneider & vom-Brocke (2019) International Journal of Information Management, 49, 424-438 Elsevier ScienceDirect
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30.	A Conceptual Framework for Data Governance in IoT-enabled Digital Ecosystems.	Dasgupta, Gill & Hussain (2019)	DATA 2019 - 8th International Conference on Data Science, Technology and Applications. 209-216	Science and Technology Publications,
31.	Data Governance and Information Governance: Set of Definitions in Relation to Data and Information as Part of DIKW.	Merkus, Helms & Kusters (2019)	Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems (ICEIS 2019). 143-154	Science and Technology Publications
32.	Data governance is key to interpretation: Reconceptualizing data in data science	Leonelli (2019)	Harvard Data Science Review, 1(1), 10-1162	
33.	Data Governance Taxonomy: Cloud versus Non-Cloud	Al-Ruithe, Benkhelifa & Hameed (2018)	Sustainability, 10(95), 1-26	MDPI
34.	Data governance cloud security assessment at data center	Saed, Aziz, Ramadhani & Hassan (2018)	2018 4th International Conference on Computer and Information Sciences (ICCOINS) 1-4	IEEE
35.	Data Governance in the Health Industry: Investigating Data Quality Dimensions within a Big Data Context	Juddoo, George, Duquenoy, & Windridge (2018)	Applied System Innovation 1(43) 1-16	MDPI
36.	Exploring Big Data Governance Frameworks	Al-Badi, Tarhini & Khan (2018)	Procedia Computer Science, 141, 271-277	Elsevier ScienceDirect

Findings

The systematic literature review adopted a broad search strategy to extract the maximum relevant data from the six databases. A total of 36 articles were identified that fulfilled the criteria of the study (figure 2) and their bibliographic information was imported into a

spreadsheet. The overview of the included studies as presented in Table 2 revealed the characteristics of the selected studies. The titles of the articles showed that Research Data Governance penetrated different filed of knowledge but was dominated by IT/Computer Science disciplines. The years of publication of the articles ranged between 2018 to 2022 with most of the studies (n = 12) being published in 2022 while the least studies (n = 4) were published in 2018.

The largest number of contributing authors in one article (n = 8) was published in 2020 by Kariotis, Ball, Tzovaras, Dennis, Sahama, Johnston, Almond & Borda (2020) on the title “Emerging health data platforms: From individual control to collective data governance”. The analysis revealed only 4 single-authored articles (n = 4) were found during the reviewed years treating direct variables of data governance from the studies of Patel (2022); Wang (2022); Engels (2019) and Leonelli (2019). This showed that Research Data Governance studies were largely collaborative due to the wide domain coverage and the recent discovery of data governance as an asset for organizational development.

Conceptual Definition of Research Data Governance

Table 3: Concept and Definition of Data Governance

S/No	Authors / Year	Concept of RDG
1.	Ahmadi, Tavana, Shokouhyar & Dortaj (2022); Eechoud (2022); Hikmawati, Santosa & Hidayah (2021)	Guidelines and rules for data management, who can make decisions about data manipulation within organizations
2.	Manik, Akbar, Yaman & Indrawati (2022); Aguboshim, Obiokafor & Ezeife (2022); Eke et al. (2022)	Assignment of control for different decision domains were models, policies, and standards governing how data are stored
3.	Awada, Phillips & Bogdan (2022); Bento, Neto & Côte-Real (2022); Al-Badi, Tarhini & Khan (2018)	Record and manage knowledge derived from data, strategies, and policies related to management and decisions taking about the dataset
4.	Al-Wahshi, Foster & Abbott (2022); Al-Sousi & Shah (2022); Patel (2022)	Maximize the value of enterprise data while minimizing their potential risks by ensuring data quality, security, and compliance
5.	Wang (2022); Shi, Li, Wang & Zhang (2022); Castro, Villagra, Garca, Rivera & Toledo (2021); Omar & Almaghthawi (2020)	Forming an integrated internal system to work for the collection and application of information, planning, design, process control, and quality supervision of the whole life cycle of data resource

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6. Filgueiras & Lui (2022); Kouper, Raymond & Giroux (2020); Leonelli (2019); Al-Ruithe, Benkhelifa & Hameed (2018) The Decision-making process focused on authority building to specify decision rights on data use, security, integrity, and availability; Coordination, regulation, curation, and management of research data
 7. Bozkurt, Rossmann & Pervez (2022); Saed, Aziz, Ramadhani & Hassan (2018) A company-wide strategic framework for all data-relevant topics, in which guidelines, standards, processes, responsibilities, and technologies represent the main action fields in aligning data with corporate governance and enterprise architecture
 8. Shah & AlSousi (2021); Ramadhan, Jaafar & Tajudeen (2021); Chang & Kang (2021); Brous & Janssen (2020); Micheli, Ponti, Craglia & Suman (2020); Janssen, Brous, Estevez, Barbosa & Janowski (2020); Abraham, Schneider & vom-Brocke (2019) Practice of authority and supervision, power and control process needed to manage and control data, and redistributing value produced through data
 9. Benfeldt, Persson & Madsen (2020); Thabit, Ishhadat & Abdulrahman (2020); Juddoo, George, Duquenoy, & Windridge (2018) Determine how data can be used to achieve broader organizational objectives and assign accountabilities and rights decisions for the information-related processes
 10. Kariotis, Ball, Tzovaras, Dennis, Sahama, Johnston, Almond & Borda (2020); Gupta & Cannon (2020); Yebenes & Zorrilla (2019); Al-Ruithe, Benkhelifa & Hameed (2019) Policies and approaches that enable stewardship, management of data as a strategic asset, providing quality control and protection
 11. Engels (2019); Merkus, Helms & Kusters (2019); Dasgupta, Gill & Hussain (2019) Data availability and data quality for all possible management tasks and decision-making and operations
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The review of the concept and definition of data governance provides a conceptual framework for data governance and a comprehensive overview of concepts from the definition of Data Governance. The difference between data management and data governance remains unclear in the literature reviewed (Al-Ruithe et al., 2018). Deriving from particular aspects of this analysis, the study briefly outlined the agenda for future research on data governance. During the qualitative analysis of the abstracts and contents of the studies, a concept-centric analysis was undertaken and a pattern emerged. About 80% of the reviewed articles examined data governance at the organizational level, explaining data governance as a way to manage data between discrete organizations.

Some of the reviewed studies focused on the definition of Data Governance including data storage, control, and data sharing practices (Patel, 2022; Aguboshim, Obiokafor & Ezeife, 2022; Manik et al., 2022; Shi, Li, Wang & Zhang, 2022; Wang, 2022; Janssen et al., 2020; Leonelli, 2019; Juddoo et al., 2018) while the majority of the studies comprehensively explore the RDG including data policies, size of the data, data organization, data processing, and data security (Al-Sousi & Shah, 2022; Al-Wahshi, Foster & Abbott, 2022; Filgueiras & Lui, 2022; Bozkurt, Rossmann & Pervez, 2022; Omar & Almaghthawi, 2020; Kariotis et al., 2020; Thabit, Ishhadat & Abdulrahman, 2020; Al-Badi, Tarhini & Khan, 2018). It can be deduced from the reviewed definitions that data governance is defined standards and procedures to ensure the proactive and effective handling and guidance of data and information management practices such as data distribution, data security, data backup, metadata management, data mapping, and data business.

Research Discipline in Research Data Governance

However, coherency among concepts and domains of research data governance is necessary for the provision of the right sets of data to the right people capturing, analyzing, storing, searching, sharing, increasing revenue, managing cost, and ensuring compliance with data governance processes and procedures. The definitions of data governance showed the need for consistency, in using the concepts of data integrity, security, sharing responsibilities, and addressing principles and ethical aspects as well as data management. For libraries to achieve data governance, it requires assigning complex, organizational reality control over data processes such as data quality, data security, data architecture, data modeling, and operations to develop and implement corporate-wide data policies, guidelines, and standards. The implication for this uniformity in practice is that this gives a better mutual understanding of vocabulary within and across the different components of the library.

Table 4: Distribution of Disciplines Across Articles

SN	Distribution of Disciplines	Frequency and percentages	Authors / Year of Publication
1.	IT/Computer Science Institutions	15 (41.7%)	Ahmadi, Tavana, Shokouhyar & Dortaj (2022); Patel (2022); Wang (2022); Castro, Villagra, Garca, Rivera & Toledo (2021); Janssen, Brous, Estevez, Barbosa & Janowski (2020); Brous & Janssen (2020); Thabit, Ishhadat & Abdulrahman (2020) Yebenes & Zorrilla (2019); Al-Ruithe, Benkhelifa & Hameed (2019); Dasgupta, Gill & Hussain (2019); Merkus, Helms &

2.	Public Security Institutions	2 (5.6%)	<i>Kusters (2019); Leonelli (2019); Al-Ruithe, Benkhelifa & Hameed (2018); Saed, Aziz, Ramadhani & Hassan (2018); Al-Badi, Tarhini & Khan (2018) Manik, Akbar, Yaman & Indrawati (2022); Shi, Li, Wang & Zhang (2022) Awada, Phillips & Bogdan (2022)</i>
3.	Agricultural Sector	1 (2.8%)	<i>Al-Sousi & Shah (2022); Aguboshim, Obiokafor & Ezeife (2022); Bento, Neto & Côte-Real (2022); Al-Wahshi, Foster & Abbott (2022); Hikmawati, Santosa & Hidayah (2021); Shah & AlSousi (2021); Micheli, Ponti, Craglia & Suman (2020); Engels (2019); Huang et al (2020)</i>
4.	Business/Economic Institutions	8 (22.2%)	<i>Filgueiras & Lui (2022); Bozkurt, Rossmann & Pervez (2022); Wirtz et al. (2022); Ramadhan, Jaafar & Tajudeen (2021); Chang & Kang (2021); Kouper, Raymond & Giroux (2020); Omar & Almaghthawi (2020); Benfeldt, Persson & Madsen (2020); Abraham, Schneider & vom-Brocke (2019)</i>
5.	Public/Smart Cities Institutions	8 (22.2%)	<i>Kariotis, Ball, Tzovaras, Dennis, Sahama, Johnston, Almond & Borda (2020); Juddoo, George, Duquenoy, & Windridge (2018)</i>
6.	Public Health	2 (5.6%)	-
7.	Library and Information Science	0 (0.0)	-
Total		36 (100%)	

During the analysis of the abstracts and contents of the 36 records, different research areas (disciplines) of concern were surveyed in relation to data governance by the articles. The distribution of disciplines across the different research articles surveyed indicates both theoretical and practical implications within the adoption process of data governance in libraries and other information centers. The records showed that Information Technology and Computer Science disciplines were the highly researched areas regarding Research Data Governance (RDG) with 15 (41.7%) records followed by public/smart cities institutions 8 (22.2%) and business/economic institutions 8 (22.2%) records. Public health and public security institutions had 2 (5.6%) records each while agricultural sector researches had only 1 (2.8%) record between 2018 to 2022 on research data governance (RDG).

Authorship Dimension of Research and Characteristics of Reviewed Data Governance

Table 5: Distribution of Sources and Number of Contributors per Article

Year Distribution	Frequency	Percent	Contributors	Frequency	Percent
2018	4	11.1%	One Author	4	11.1%
2019	7	19.4%	Two Authors	7	19.4%
2020	8	22.2%	Three Authors	16	44.4%
2021	5	13.9%	Four Authors	6	16.7%
2022	12	33.3%	Five Authors	2	5.6%
			Above Five Author	1	2.8%
Total	36	100.0%	Total	36	100.0%

Discussion

This study provides an overview of the state-of-the-art data governance field using PRISMA Diagram by considering a systematic treatment of the literature and identifying a research agenda. The systematic literature review revealed 36 closely related articles to research data governance (RDG), and six (6) areas of concern by authors for future development of data governance were listed. The relevant literature on data governance generally showed a continuous growth trend from 2018 to 2022, the study discovered that RDG is gradually gaining importance among researchers and academics; however, it is still poorly practiced by researchers in libraries and the information profession. The use of data has the potential to facilitate better decision-making and improve service delivery in libraries and information centers, especially around open access, this calls for the urgent need for Research Data

Governance research and practice in the field of library and information sciences to improve data storage, retrieval and worthiness.

The study answered the first question by identifying basic concepts used in defining research data governance including data storage, control and data sharing practices as well as data policies, size of the data, data organization, data processing, and data security. The definitions of data governance showed the need for consistency, in using concepts of data integrity, security, sharing responsibilities and addressing principles and ethical aspects as well as data management. The second research question was answered by identifying six different research areas (disciplines) of concern in relation to data governance by the articles which indicated both theoretical and practical implications within the adoption process of data governance in libraries and other information centers. The records showed that Information Technology and Computer Science disciplines were the highly researched areas regarding RDG followed by public/smart cities institutions, business/economic institutions, public health institutions, public security institutions and agricultural sector research conducted between 2018 to 2022 on research data governance (RDG).

The findings showed no article treating directly, RDG directly in libraries but only in the related fields of Information Technology and Computer Science. Academic Scholars and researchers may use these findings to position future work in the field of data governance and propose theoretical and practice-oriented frameworks for the implementation of RDG in libraries and information centers. Research data governance identified in most of the studies were data storage, preservation and data sharing practices, data policies, size of the data, data organization, data processing, data sharing, and data security. Moreover, it is understandable from the reviewed articles that governing research data involves complex cooperation among various stakeholders including research support staff, IT department, IT infrastructure, and higher administration. This study, therefore, opens a “black box” of research for academic libraries to open through collaboration with researchers in the IT/Computer Science and research offices to take the necessary initiative that helps the coordination and adoption of research data governance principles and practice.

Conclusion

The lack of research data governance in libraries is a real concern for researchers and library professionals which serves as the major reason behind the poor management of research data. Information Technology and Computer Science were by far the most prominent disciplines surveyed by the studies on RDG from 2018 to 2022. This finding supports the notion that the data governance field is in large part built on the same foundation of IT/Computer Science. Aligning IT with the performance goals of data governance and its outcomes could suggest the field is still largely driven by IT-oriented researchers.

The state of the Research Data Governance field can be uncertainly evaluated from the findings of this study for its status in libraries and information centers. The distribution of relatively few publications amongst the overabundance of authors suggests the field has not matured enough for researchers to publish articles within the domain of libraries and information centers. However, the top publishing authors count as both practitioners and academics, which suggests it is a field attracting the attention of both communities. Therefore, stakeholders within the domain of library and information center should sit together and make compulsory grant funding to researchers and IT infrastructure, resolve data ownership issues and prepare mechanisms and procedures for studies of RDG to improve policy planning and productivity around librarianship.

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